

2 Legal documents of the spatial planning system
(Lei de Bases / RJIGT)

4 Spatial planning instruments

PNPOT
(National Spatial Planning Policy Program)

PROT-LMA
(Regional Spatial Planning Program
for Lisbon Metropolitan Area)

PEOT POPNA
(Sectoral Plan for the Natural Conservation
Area of Arrábida)

PDM Setúbal
(Municipal Master Plan)

Lei de bases gerais da política pública de solos, de ordenamento do território e de urbanismo (2014).

It lays down the general bases for public policy on land use and urban planning. One of its main goals (article 2) is to enhance the potential of the soil, safeguarding its quality and its environmental, economic, social and cultural functions as a physical support and cultural framework for people and their activities, a source of raw materials and biomass production, carbon reservoir and biodiversity reserve.

National Program for Spatial Planning Policy (PNPOT, 2019): it is a comprehensive and intersectoral Programme that is the top instrument of the planning system in Portugal;

Regional Land Planning Plan for the Metropolitan Area of Lisbon (PROT AML, 2002): a comprehensive and intersectoral Plan that establishes specific guidelines for defining land use and development regimes locally, considering relevant national and regional strategies with direct impacts on Biodiversity.

Plano de Ordenamento do Parque Natural da Arrábida (POPNA, 2005). It is a supplementary means of government intervention for the protection of public interests of a national nature, which establishes regimes for safeguarding resources, natural values and management regimes with a direct impact on Biodiversity. They develop the guidelines and actions permitted, conditioned or prohibited for protected areas and whose implementation must be done by planning instruments at a local scale.

Plano Director Municipal de Setúbal (PDM, 2023).

Delivers the local strategy, establishing the principles and goals underlying the Regional and National scope in a coherent spatial development model. It also includes specific guidelines of sectoral and special nature and identifies the inherent options for organising, classifying and qualifying land use regimes directly impacting biodiversity.